

The Coupling Constant Series and Intergalactic Absorptions

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework, 8T, and the insights gain regarding the nature of the electrons and photons as the majestic (3) and as net variation $N_V = (+5)$, accordingly, in the coupling term describing the Electric, it is possible to reason for the cosmological phenomena of intergalactic absorptions and redshifts. Analysis of the Electron behavior will be made using a varying Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected Einstein manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times R$, by the Euler Lagrange operator. The main tool of analysis is done via primordial coupling constant series on the manifold, derived in March 2021.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Examine the term describing the electric coupling. We proved majestic (3) is the electron in the 8-Theory thesis.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + 5 \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.121)$$

Since the setting is the Lorentz manifold, a curved space-time, those net variations cannot move in a linear path, there has by certain deflections. Those deflections are caused by arbitrary variations than vanishing into matter. Such vanishing is represented in the main equation of the framework, represented by the manifold inside Euler LaGrange operator.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (2)$$

We partitioned and discretized the term δg to derive the nature of fermions. In particular, partitioning of terms shows that the amount of sub elements must be even, differ in sign and summed as zero.

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Define a set of photons propagating across the matrix from a certain position, and aspiring a certain destination on the manifold.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i > 0 \quad (2.11)$$

Associate the set of photons a certain cluster density, or a wavelength in a physical theory. How much curvature per unit metric.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i \rightarrow \omega_{M1}^{M2} \quad (3)$$

M1, M2 are four vectors, representing a segment of the matrix

$$M1 \rightarrow M_\mu$$

$$M2 \rightarrow M_\nu$$

An additional measurement at later continuation of time, of the density cluster of photons per unit matrix, would be a representation of the shift, and the absorption, if one constructed properly. The idea was to reason mathematically how an external curvature would effect a dense cluster of variation.

$$\omega_{M1}^{M2} - \omega_{M1}^{M2} \Delta t = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} \quad (3.1)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)